

Another 6Q15 (Damascus Document) Fragment Amidst the 4Q Unidentified Fragments

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Recently I demonstrated that two fragments among the Qumran Cave 4 unidentified fragments should be assigned to 6Q15 (6QD).¹ The purportedly Cave 4 and Cave 6 fragments form a perfect join, textually and materially, and display the same irregular script.

Yet another Cave 4 unidentified fragment should also be assigned to this manuscript: PAM 43.686 frag. 50 (IAA Plate 18 frag. 34) has all the same material, scribal, and palaeographic features as the other fragments, and can be identified as preserving part of CD 6:3-5.

נבונים ומישראל חכמים וישמיעם ויחפורו] אִתְּ] הבאר	1
באר חפרוה שרים כרוה נדיבי העם במחוק] ק הבא] ר	2
היא התורה וחופריה הם שבי ישראל] היצ] אים	3

One may note the defective spelling of היצאים, and that reconstruction of the missing text on the basis of the CD manuscript results in uneven lines. That, however, is also true of some of the other 6Q15 fragments.

¹Eibert Tigchelaar, "Two Damascus Document Fragments and Mistaken Identities: The Mingling of Some Qumran Cave 4 and Cave 6 Fragments." *Dead Sea Discoveries* 28 (2021): 64-74. Online 10.1163/15685179-20201001.